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IMPLICATIONS ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY IN CRM

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Abstract

Customer relationship management (CRM) is an integration of people, processes and technologies aimed at mitigating customers in the company. CRM has evolved from the advances in information technology and customer-focused organizational changes. CRM companies will reap the benefits from customer loyalty and long-term profitability. However, many enterprises cannot achieve successfully, mainly because they do not realize that CRM requires corporate, cross-functional, customer-focused re-engineering. CRM is seen as a business trend, but an industry standard which ensures and maintains a competitive advantage. CRM determines strategic, operational, analytical and collaborative determination. The benefits of CRM will be linked to improved customer-oriented capabilities, coordination of cross-chain support, increased efficiency and efficiency of sales, improved pricing, customized products and services, increased efficiency and effectiveness for customer service, individual marketing messages also called campaigns, connect customers and all channels on a single platform.

Keywords: CRM, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, service quality, service access and handling complaints

1.1 Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

Customer relationship management is an upright concept or strategy to strengthen customer relations and, at the same time, to reduce costs and improve business productivity and profitability. A centralized collection of all data sources within an organization and an atomic real-time vision of customer information is an ideal CRM system. A CRM system is vast and important, but can also be implemented for small businesses and large companies, as the main aim being to help customers effectively. Usually an organization consists of various departments which mainly have direct or indirect access to customer information. A CRM system centrally collects this information, examines it and then makes it addressable throughout the department. CRM systems include

- Data storage technology used to aggregate transaction information, merge information with CRM products and provide key indicators of performance.
- Opportunity management to assist the company in managing unpredictable growth and demand, and a good projection model to integrate sales history with sales projections.
- CRM systems that track and measure marketing campaigns across multiple networks, track customer analysis and sales.
- Some CRM software (SaaS) can be delivered via the Internet and accessed through the web browser rather than on the local computer. Businesses using the software do not buy it, but typically pay the software vendor a recurrent subscription fee.
- A CRM system may consist of an email, documents, jobs, faxes and scheduling system for individual accounts for small businesses. CRM systems for specific markets (legal, financial) frequently focus in contrast to financial return on investment on event management and relationship tracking (ROI).
- eCommerce CRM systems focused on marketing automation tasks, such as: cart rescue, e-mail re-commitment, customization.
- Customer-centered relationship management (CCRM) is an emerging subsection that focuses on customer preferences rather than on customer leverage. By involving customers in individual, interactive relationships, CCRM seeks to add value.
- Non-profit and member-based systems assist with tracking of constituents, fund raising, demographics of sponsors, membership levels, member directories, volunteering and personal communication.

1.2 Customer Satisfaction

Oliver R.L. and Swan (1989) report that satisfaction is a person's sense of pleasure or disappointment with the perceived performance of an undertaking in relation to his or her expectation. In addition, they found that the judgment is that a product or service feature is at a pleasant level of consumption, including levels of performance under or over compliance. Satisfaction is a perceived degree of satisfaction with the prior experience of the customer. It is fully understood that customer satisfaction is a perception of the individual that his/her expectations about a product or a service are fulfilled. Reicheld et.al (1990) found customer satisfaction as a tool for productivity and as a source of competitive advantage.

With an understanding of the relationship between customer and customer satisfaction, organizations need to focus more on CRM requirements than on the retention of existing customers. Management of customer relationships is a process of achieving and maintaining an on-going connection with customers over multiple customer contact points through differential and tailored customer treatment of their likely responses to alternative marketing programmes. This applies to all types of service organizations and would certainly assist them to maintain a better level of the market. In addition, the opinions of individuals who are likely to have close contact with customers such as dealers and staff with customer contacts are analyzed. Demographic analysis and their effects are also carried out. CRM plays a major role in driving satisfaction as satisfied

customers are beneficial to a company not only because they can make repeated purchases, but also because the company is promoted by word of mouth.

First, companies can customize their products for each customer. By collecting information and processing this information to discover hidden patterns, CRM applications help companies to customize their products to their customer's individual tastes. This customization improves the perceived quality of products and services in terms of customer, which means that the perceived quality indirectly affects customer satisfaction. Oliver R.L. and Swan (1989) report that satisfaction is a person's sense of pleasure or disappointment with the perceived performance of an undertaking in relation to his or her expectation. In addition, they found that the judgment is that a product or service feature is at a pleasant level of consumption, including levels of performance under or over compliance. Satisfaction is a perceived degree of satisfaction with the prior experience of the customer. It is fully understood that customer satisfaction is a perception of the individual that his/her expectations about a product or a service are fulfilled.

Reicheld et.al (1990) found customer satisfaction as a tool for productivity and as a source of competitive advantage. With an understanding of the relationship between customer and customer satisfaction, organizations need to focus more on CRM requirements than on the retention of existing customers. Management of customer relationships is a process of achieving and maintaining an on-going connection with customers over multiple customer contact points through differential and tailored customer treatment of their likely responses to alternative marketing programmes.

This applies to all types of service organizations and would certainly assist them to maintain a better level of the market. In addition, the opinions of individuals who are likely to have close contact with customers such as dealers and staff with customer contacts are analyzed. Demographic analysis and their effects are also carried out. CRM plays a major role in driving satisfaction as satisfied customers are beneficial to a company not only because they can make repeated purchases, but also because the company is promoted by word of mouth. First, companies can customize their products for each customer. By collecting information and processing this information to discover hidden patterns, CRM applications help companies to customize their products to their customer's individual tastes. This customization improves the perceived quality of products and services in terms of customer, which means that the perceived quality indirectly affects customer satisfaction.

1.3 CRM on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty:

CRM is being implemented in an organization to reduce costs and improve corporate performance, which means profitability is a result of customer loyalty, according to Bhattacharya (2011) research. Data are collected from internal and external sources, such as sales department, customer service, marketing, after-sales services, procurement and others in successful CRM implementation. This is vital if each customer requires a holistic view in a real-time system. This information can help employees decide quickly and accurately when dealing with customers in different areas and points of contact. The findings of this study show that customer perception

and treatment each customer can solve many customer problems individually. The successful implementation of CRM would achieve customer satisfaction and loyalty. Therefore, organizations should identify different customer requirements and adjust their policies to improve the competitiveness of the company. Under Faed's (2010) conceptual framework, customer relationship management amplifies customers' and competitors' relationships within an enterprise to improve their market share of the organization through integration of technology, procedures and people. CRM's goal is to preserve customers and improve their loyalty and business profit. Customer satisfaction and satisfaction are two key elements of successful customer loyalty implementation.

1) project focused 2) internal metrics, employee adoption the internal factors responsible for the CRM 3) Customer satisfaction and loyalty externally oriented metrics. The most important externally oriented criteria are as follows, according to the findings: 1) verified customer loyalty and satisfaction influence 3) Increased information and perception; 2) measurable revenue development 4) Cost drop measurable 5) enhanced employee efficiency 6) employee practice 7) data compliance.

1.4 CRM Software:

Currently, E-CRM is a modernized application, i.e. internet-based technologies, such as e-mails, web sites, chat rooms, forums and other channels for achieving the CRM goals. It is a well-structured and coordinated CRM process that automates marketing, sales and customer service processes. Effective E-CRM increases process efficiency as well as improves customer interaction and enables companies to customize products and services that meet their individual customer requirements. A typical E-CRM strategy involves collecting information from customers, transaction history and product details, click stream and content. It then analyzes the customer features to provide a transactional analysis of the customer profile and transactional history and an analysis of the activity consisting of customer navigation, shopping cart, patterns and many more exploratory activities.

Our ECRM application is the quickest, easiest and most flexible way to manage your customer and sales information irrespective of size, site or industry. Our web-based platform allows Working Groups to easily create unlimited applications for automating and improving business processes. Our applications address critical business problems as they can be adapted to the exact youthful CRM workflow.

This application offers a comprehensive view of customer interactions across departments, providing information and facilities to improve planning, management and forecasting. Tools we use provide an opportunity to increase sales, reach rentable customers, increase customer experience and anticipate customer needs. Our product offers flexible business access, deployment and payment options.

Conclusion

The measure of how the needs and responses are collaborated and delivered to exceed customer requirements is customer satisfaction. It can be achieved only if the customer has a good overall relationship with the supplier. Customer satisfaction is a significant

performer and fundamental differentiator of business strategies in today's competitive business marketplace. The more customer satisfaction, the more business and customer bonding. Such satisfaction can be linked to different business aspects such as marketing, product manufacture, engineering, product and service quality, customer answers and questions, project completion, postal delivery services, complaints management etc. Customer satisfaction has important consequences for companies' economic performance, as it can increase customer loyalty and customer usage behavior, reducing customer complaints and customer defection. The implementation of a CRM approach will likely influence customer satisfaction and customer knowledge for a number of reasons.

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ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

Creativity and innovations are indispensable for the growth of business and the success of the organization. It is an important factor which helps traditional companies and educational institutions in foreseeing the potential threats and rising competition. Needless to say, companies and organizations cannot thrive without matching the pace with the change and transformation which is taking place in the market. Digital transformation integrates digital technologies into all areas of a business. To meet with the ever changing demands of business processes and customer expectations and create a competitive advantage as well as positioning the organization for the future growth, the role of digital transformation and innovation cannot be ignored. IoT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Automation, Machine Learning, Block Chain are some of the latest technologies which have brought about the sea of change by amalgamating demanding millennial generation into the high speed data lanes. In the past few months of Lockdown, digitalization has played a vital role in sustaining the global economic condition. Businesses are now looking for the new ways of dealings and cost minimization. Educational institutions also embraced digital mode of teaching and learning methodologies in order to minimize the impact of pandemic on the academics of students. This conference is intended to seek intellectual contribution of experts from industry, academia and research for embracing change & transformation through innovations and creativity.

ABOUT US

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School runs AICTE approved PGDM program. It has been ranked 1st Emerging B-School among top institutes of west India by Time of India. It has also been conferred the ET Now Business School of the year award. The two-year full-time PGDM program offered by Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School is designed to empower students to become successful business professionals in the challenging global scenario. The Institute is continually evolving to meet its goals in an ever-changing business environment. It has been playing an important role in professionalizing Indian Management through its programs. Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School aims to create value-driven leaders, global managers and entrepreneurs with strong conceptual foundations and analytical approach to help them be the best in whichever field they choose. The aim is to innovatively address the needs of a modern India and connecting aspirations and realities to attain benchmarks that are respected internationally.

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